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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE SURGICAL TREATMENT AND
CLINICAL FEATURES OF CLEFT LIP AND PALATE*****Dr. Ghulam Hussain, *Dr. Mehr-un-Nisah*****Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan****Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study was to know the surgical treatment and clinical features of the cleft lip and palate.

Study design: A Prospective Study.

Location and Duration: In the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018.

Methodology: A total of 50 patients with congenital cleft lip and palate were treated in the oral and maxillofacial surgery department. The cleft in the lip was repaired with a functional repair technique and the cleft in the palate was repaired with intra velor-veloplasty. Cleft lip and palate is a congenital anomaly that involves the patient's disciplines of medicine and dentistry and requires coordinated care.

Results: Unfortunately, the incidence of clefts is increasing in developing countries due to lack of awareness and insufficient pregnancy management of the mother. Lack of resources on both sides, ie patients and medical professionals, does not help to rule out the cause of this problem. Although the inseparable care of cleft patients is far from being a reality in the lower continent, we report cleft lip and palate cases treated in coordination with different competencies.

Conclusion: In this study, we emphasized the demographic, clinical features and surgical management of cleft lip and cleft palates.

Key Words: Management, Cleft lip and palate, Oral and maxillofacial surgery.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cleft lip and palate are the most common congenital birth defects in humans. In a recent study describing population-based data on the incidence of cleft lip and cleft palate from Elahi and others in Pakistan, a recent study found 1.91 (one for each 523 births) in 1000 births. The incidence of cleft lip and palate in the multi-ethnic population of Hawaii was 12.5 in 10,000 live births on cleft lips and 1.94 in 1000 live births in the Philippines. For Victoria's children in Australia, the report showed 7.8 points in 10,000 pregnancies. The management of oral clefts is very important and sensitive, because once these children are born, they start their suction with difficulty in their basic absorption instincts and tend to develop profound changes in their images. There is also the mother's fault for giving birth to a deformed child. The treatment of oral clefts begins when the first pediatrician who treats the baby directs the baby to the oral surgery unit and a feeding device is requested. Preoperative treatment of orthopedics involves the production and placement of molding tools. Therefore, the protodontist and orthodontist have a definite role. The history of cleft lip and palate surgery shows the name of many outstanding surgeons, among them French dentist Lemonier, the first is invested in palatal repair. In addition to primary cleft lip and cleft palate repair, present oral and maxillofacial surgery offers alveolar reconstructive pharyngoplasty and orthognathic surgery, the last steps in treatment. The management of the cleft lip and palate has become a recognized sub-specialist of oral and maxillofacial surgery due to the presence of orthodontists and allied support under

Bilateral cleft lip and palate (missing or incomplete missing).

the same roof, but is still unaware. The Z-plasty technique has always been used to achieve acceptable aesthetic results. The technique of developing Millard's rotation, the complex mathematical formulas of Tennison and Randal have a basic Z-plasty concept. The names of Le Mesurier, Skoog and Hagedorn attract attention because of their significant contribution to cleft lip surgery. "The foundations of cleft surgery in modern days are deeply rooted in dentistry. Due to the good work of Hullihen, Truman Brophy, Chalmers Lyons and Robert Ivy, traditional repair has undergone functional cleft surgery and includes tissue engineering, genetics and fetal surgery. The time recommended by several authors is variable from one day to one year, and the results of cleft lip surgery are difficult to assess objectively due to a number of relevant variables. The epidemiology and surgical treatment of the cleft lip is described in detail in the Western literature, but not much has been written in the local literature. We propose to present our experience in this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Prospective Study was held in the Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018. A total of 50 patients with cleft lip and palate were selected. Three patients with associated anomalies were excluded from the study. The classification represents the indents as follows:

Alveolar cleft lip.

Cleft lip (complete or missing)

Submucosal cleft.

Cleft palate (Soft or Hard, Right, Left, Full or Incomplete).

Unilateral cleft lip and palate (complete or incomplete).

Surgical treatment of cleft lip patients was performed using the functional repair technique of the lips as recommended by Delaire .

All clefts were basically closed and no lip adhesion was made. Only very wide cleft lip were closed with Z (Tennison) plasty technique -14, while others were closed with a straight line. In most cases, preoperative orthopedic treatment was necessary. General endotracheal anesthesia was performed in all cases. Intubation, accidental extubation and apnea were observed. After marking the edges of the lip clefts, the three layers of the tissue were dissected and then approached again separately. The Vicryl and proline sutures were used to cover the fins in layers. Palatoplasty was performed using intravelor veloplastoplasty. Abnormal joints at the posterior edge of the hard palate include the muscles of the muscles to be raised and inserted in the middle, and all other layers stitched separately. All mothers had the option of breastfeeding their babies after surgery. In cases where breastfeeding was difficult, a syringe-fastened NG tube was used. A systematic operation was taken before and after the surgery. The patients were discharged three days later. All patients were followed up to the possible limits.

RESULTS:

We treated 47 patients during a one-year course. Of these 47 patients, 20 (42.5%) were male and 27 (57.5%) were

female (Table 1), male to female ratio 1: 1.35. Of the 47 men, 22 were treated in June and 25 in after January.

Table 1: Gender Distribution of Clefts

The highest number of age groups (Table 2) was older than 1 year of age and reached 28 years of age.

Table 2: Sample Distribution based on Chronological Age

According to the site (Table 3), 10 (21.27%) patients with bilateral cleft lip and palate, 8 (17.02%) cleft palate, 14 (29.78%) unilateral cleft lip and palate, and in our center with alveolar cleft and cleft palate 13 patients (27.65%) with cleft lips were treated.

Table 3: Distribution of Clefts According to Site

Only one patient with bilateral cleft lip had a small dissociation that did not require resuscitation. There was no death. There were two vermilion imbalances, three residual palatal fistulas and infection.

DISCUSSION:

However, although this is a relatively small group of patients, it shows that cleft lip stamps in society can be reduced by organizing and using the services of oral and maxillofacial surgeons in Pakistan. In our study, the ratio of men and women was 1: 1.35 for all cleft types that were different from other studies in the region where male dominance was reported. 59.6% of the patients older than one year had. Only two patients were adolescents. Significant observation in these patients was that the maxillary hypoplasia associated with the cleft was not relative. In the cleft lip cases, the left side was more common than the right side and isolated cleft palate was more common in women. These observations were also reported by another local study. Full unilateral cleft lip and palate were more common than bilaterally. Our demographic results are not very typical because of the limited treatment rights in our hospital and a reference center for a very wide area. We use generously other possibilities such as prosthetics and orthodontics. The results were quite encouraging and we recommend orthopedics before surgery for cleft lip and cleft palate.

The treatment protocol currently used in most cleft treatment centers, including AFID, is shown below.

- Neonate: diagnostic test, general advice to parents,

feeding instructions, palatal obturator (if necessary); diagnostic features; A protocol proposal for the treatment of a cleft.

- Age 9 months - begins speech therapy.
- Age 6 months: if necessary, preoperative orthodontics; first speech assessment
- Age 3 months - repair of CL (and placement of ventilation tubes)
- 9-12 months - repair of CP (placement of ventilation tubes if not performed during CL repair)
- 7-8 years old - Alveolar bone graft.
- Age 1-7 years - Orthodontic treatment.
- More than 8 years - Orthodontic treatment continues.

CONCLUSION:

One of the most common congenital conditions affecting the orofacial region is the cleft oral cavity. The oral cavity is the area of the mouth surgeon. Particularly in oral surgery and dentistry in general, in and around the oral cavity includes in-depth training and research. Most of the experts in the treatment of cleft oral cavity belong to dentistry, because of this uniqueness; the solution of the cleft oral cavity problem can be answered by the cleft lip and cleft palate surgeons. When there are too many options to perform a procedure, there is no definite option and the same applies to repair the cleft lip and

palate. The concept of a coordinated effort to treat the cleft lip and palate under the roof emerges. This can easily be done as a sub-specialist of oral and maxillofacial surgery. Our results support this concept and we support this concept for Pakistan.

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